

Privacy Preserving Approximated Optimal Control of Pasteurization Unit Using Homomorphic Encryption

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Abstract: Homomorphic encryption (HE) enables computations to be carried out over encrypted data, ensuring data privacy during processing. This feature is lucrative in various fields, including general process control and network control systems. However, there are some limitations to the applicability of modern noisy HE schemes, especially for computationally more challenging control techniques, such as Model Predictive Control. One of the solutions to this problem is to use homomorphically encrypted neural networks trained to mimic the behavior of MPC. This paper showcases such a neural network and demonstrates its capabilities for data privacy preserving control of the laboratory pasteurization unit.

Keywords: Homomorphic encryption, privacy, CKKS, model predictive control, neural network, implementation.

1. INTRODUCTION

Standard encryption protects data during transfer or storage but cannot secure data during processing. Homomorphic encryption (HE) offers exactly this property by allowing computations in the encrypted domain. The data can remain encrypted throughout the processing phases, bringing new privacy-preserving applications, especially in multiparty scenarios. This feature makes HE a viable candidate for process control applications.

The concept of encrypted control is relatively novel, considering one of the first propositions to use homomorphic encryption in process control was in 2015 in Kogiso and Fujita (2015). In this paper, the authors applied RSA and ElGamal encryption schemes on state feedback controllers for numerical simulation. Over the years, the field of HE control has grown significantly, and various types of encryption schemes have been used. The Paillier cryptosystem Paillier (1999) is commonly applied for integer-oriented applications. The HEAAN (Homomorphic Encryption for Arithmetic of Approximate Numbers), also known as CKKS Cheon et al. (2017), is preferably used for applications with computations over real numbers.

In the literature, we can find various examples of encrypted control. The more straightforward approaches include dynamic feedback controllers, the encrypted linear dynamic controllers in Kim et al. (2022b); Tran et al. (2020), and semi-homomorphically encrypted nonlinear control approaches in Lin et al. (2018). For the more complex control scenarios, such as an MPC, the examples of linear MPC can be found in Alexandru et al. (2018) while a nonlinear MPC is demonstrated in Schulze Darup et al. (2018).

Using HE for more complex control tasks can be challenging due to its limitations. The main issue of implementing the encrypted optimal control based on modern noisy HE schemes is that they either provide only a limited number of consecutive multiplications or require a computationally very demanding procedure (called bootstrapping) to reset the magnitude of cryptographic noise in ciphertexts. Bootstrapping takes orders of magnitude longer than other cryptographic functions, making it impractical for control applications. Therefore, it is crucial to design control laws that require only a certain number of ciphertext multiplications in evaluated arithmetic circuits. This quality is also known as multiplicative depth. A convenient way to overcome this limitation is to use neural networks to approximate control laws since they have fixed and deterministic multiplicative depth. The main challenges that involve HE control of various kinds are summarized in Schulze Darup et al. (2021).

This paper demonstrates homomorphic encryption for near-optimal control of the laboratory pasteurization process. We achieve this by approximating the Model Predictive Controller (MPC) by a Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP) Neural Network (NN) with polynomial approximations of activation functions and evaluating the control law over encrypted process data. Using such an approach, the process data remains protected even if the control evaluation is outsourced to another party (for example, a cloud computer).

2. CKKS CRYPTOSYSTEM

This section briefly describes the CKKS (Cheon-Kim-Kim-Song) cryptosystem used in this paper. Since the CKKS is based on several non-trivial mathematical principles

and features, we describe them in terms suitable for a general audience and provide specific references to the mathematical background.

The cryptosystem’s security is based on the hardness of a problem known as Ring Learning with Errors (RLWE) (Lyubashevsky et al., 2010), which is a finite field (polynomial) version of classical Learning With Errors (LWE) problem of solving linear algebra systems in the presence of noise. RLWE-based cryptosystems are often referred to as lattice-based because they closely resemble some of the most challenging geometrical problems on lattices (Regev, 2010).

2.1 Notation and Algebraic Spaces

We denote integer, real, and complex numbers by \mathbb{Z} , \mathbb{R} and \mathbb{C} , respectively. All the operations in CKKS are carried out in an algebraic space called a polynomial ring, denoted as $\mathcal{R}_q = \mathbb{Z}_q[X]/(X^N + 1)$ (Cheon et al., 2017, Sec. 2.2). Every polynomial $r \in \mathcal{R}_q$ is of fixed degree $(N - 1)$, bounded by cyclotomic polynomial $(X^N + 1)$ with power-of-two polynomial modulus degree N . The coefficients of r are integers bounded by coefficient modulus q .

To distinguish different message spaces, we use m to denote raw messages, p for plaintext formed by encoding m , and c for ciphertext formed by encrypting p . In CKKS, the raw message $m = [m_1, m_2, \dots, m_{N/2}] \in \{\mathbb{R}, \mathbb{C}\}^{N/2}$ is a vector of $N/2$ real or complex values we want to encrypt. The encoding is the procedure that transforms message vector m into plaintext polynomial p , basically mapping $N/2$ real numbers into a single polynomial (Cheon et al., 2017, Sec. 3.2). The decoding is just a mere inversion of this procedure. The encryption is a procedure that takes p , public key (two polynomials), and two error polynomials (cryptographic noise). It produces ciphertext $c = (c_1, c_2) \in \mathcal{R}_q^2$ that is also in the form of two polynomials. Analogically, the decryption is done by evaluating ciphertext c over a secret key (polynomial). All the mathematical procedures of encoding/decoding, encryption/decryption, and key generation are provided in Cheon et al., 2017, Sec. 3.4.

It is important to note that CKKS is an approximated HE scheme. Messages propagated through the scheme are subject to cryptographic noise and various sources of approximation errors (Kim et al., 2022a), which should not pose any practical implementation problems if accounted for and handled correctly. If we encode and encrypt the original message m , the result of decryption and decoding will be just an approximation $m' \approx m$.

2.2 Properties, Features, and Challenges of CKKS

We have chosen the CKKS cryptosystem as a suitable homomorphic encryption scheme for the presented application. Compared to classical HE schemes such as the Paillier cryptosystem, the CKKS offers more versatility since it operates over real numbers and can perform an arbitrary number of homomorphic operations (if the encryption noise is handled correctly) regardless of their type. Additionally, CKKS enables relatively easy vector and matrix operations through features such as batching

(homomorphic calculation over multiple slots in a single ciphertext that is carried out parallelly in one operation) and homomorphic vector rotation (Cheon et al., 2017, see Lemma 3: Permutations over the Plaintext Slots). The ability to perform matrix/vector operations is vital for implementing neural networks, as demonstrated in this paper.

The biggest challenge of using CKKS (or any RLWE-based cryptosystem) is the demandingness of the cryptosystem parameters setup for particular applications (Furka et al., 2023). We eventually face the classic trade-offs between speed, security, and numerical correctness. The main parameters influencing the security of CKKS are polynomial modulus degree N and coefficient modulus q . The size of plaintext and ciphertext polynomials and their coefficients rise with the increasing N and q , which makes the setup more secure but computationally much slower and memory demanding. To retain the numerical precision of encoded numbers, a scaling factor Δ is used to multiply the elements of m , shifting the message bits to the left. Scaling protects the message from the cryptographic noise that is later, during the encryption, added to the message space. The underlying message of plaintext or ciphertext will be $m \times \Delta$. Additionally, the CKKS requires the implementer to define the maximum number of multiplications over a single ciphertext M (property also known as multiplicative depth).

3. DATA-PRIVACY PRESERVING CONTROL OF LABORATORY PASTEURIZATION UNIT

This section implements the privacy-preserving approximated optimal control for the laboratory pasteurization process. First, we designed a Model Predictive Control (MPC) to reject state disturbances. Since the controller evaluation requires a large number of operations that cannot be implemented in HE in any practical way, we decided to approximate the MPC by a Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP) Neural Network (NN). We chose an appropriate HE-friendly activation function as a polynomial approximation of hyperbolic tangent. Then, an NN was designed with later homomorphic evaluation in mind and trained to mimic the MPC. We performed control of the laboratory pasteurization unit first with original MPC, then NN approximation, and lastly with NN approximation on encrypted data.

3.1 Laboratory device

We use the laboratory pasteurization unit shown in Fig. 1 for the control application. The controlled part of the physical system has 3 output variables (temperatures) and 2 manipulated variables (pumps). The unit represents the industrial pasteurization plant in a more compact laboratory scale, using a *High-Temperature Short-Time* (HTST) method. Pasteurization aims to provide a specific stable temperature for the necessary time to eliminate microbial pathogens from the product. The process (Fig. 2) contains two reservoirs that feed a raw untreated liquid. The feed pump (P_F) transports this medium through a preheating chamber, a main heating chamber, a holding tube, and lastly, the cooling chambers. The central heating loop is controlled by a heating pump (P_H). The hot water is

circulated through the tank with an electric heating coil that remains constant throughout the operation. In our control setup, the heating tank temperature is represented as (T_2). When the product reaches a desired pasteurization temperature (T_3), it enters a holding tube, which is thermally insulated and ensures that the medium stays at this temperature long enough. The product of pasteurization exits the holding tube at the temperature (T_1).

Fig. 1. Laboratory device of pasteurization

Fig. 2. Process flow diagram of pasteurization unit

3.2 State-Space Model of the Pasteurization Process

The model of the pasteurization unit used in this work is based on three state variables $x = [x_1, x_2, x_3]^T$, representing the deviations of temperatures from steady state $x_i = T_i - T_i^s$, and two input variables $u = [u_1, u_2]^T = [P_H - P_H^s, P_F - P_F^s]^T$. To obtain the state space model, we used the *n4sid* subspace method from MATLAB System Identification Toolbox (Simpkins, 2012). The identification data was obtained by applying the set of combinations of step changes (both individual and concurrent) of control inputs with monitoring of all three output variables with the sampling time $T_s = 1$ s, resulting in the discrete state-space model:

$$x_{k+1} = Ax_k + Bu_k, \quad (1a)$$

$$y_k = Cx_k + Du_k, \quad (1b)$$

where

$$A = \begin{bmatrix} 0.9997 & 0.0007 & 0.0030 \\ -0.0017 & 0.9640 & 0.0377 \\ 0.0065 & -0.0139 & 0.9987 \end{bmatrix}, \quad (2a)$$

$$B = \begin{bmatrix} -0.0031 & 0.0001 \\ -0.0018 & 0.0020 \\ 0.0092 & -0.0035 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (2b)$$

Considering that all three temperatures are measured directly, the matrix $C = I_3$ and matrix $D = \mathbf{0}_{3 \times 2}$. The model was resampled to $T_s = 5$ s for the later MPC design, simulations, and process control.

3.3 Model Predictive Controller

The model predictive controller (MPC) for this particular application is formulated in the form of output steady-state control for identified discrete time state space model and u as well as x penalization in the form

$$\min_{u_0, \dots, u_{N-1}} \sum_{k=0}^{N-1} (x_k^T Q_x x_k + u_k^T Q_u u_k + s_k^T Q_s s_k) \quad (3a)$$

$$\text{s.t. } x_{k+1} = Ax_k + Bu_k, \quad (3b)$$

$$x_{\min} - s_k \leq x_k \leq x_{\max} + s_k, \quad (3c)$$

$$u_{\min} \leq u_k \leq u_{\max}, \quad (3d)$$

$$s_k \geq 0, \quad (3e)$$

$$x_0 = x(t). \quad (3f)$$

where N represents the finite prediction horizon, $Q_x \succeq 0$, $Q_u \succ 0$, $Q_s \succeq 0$ are penalty matrices. Vectors $x_k \in \mathbb{R}^{n_x}$, $u_k \in \mathbb{R}^{n_u}$, $s_k \in \mathbb{R}^{n_s}$ stand for system state, input predictions and slack variables (soft constraint) for given step k , respectively. The x_0 is the initial condition and is equal to the current measurement $x(t)$. MPC aims to ensure the stable operation of the pasteurization unit by operating in a steady state while eliminating any disturbances to achieve satisfactory production. The change in states is penalized by matrix $Q_x = \text{diag}(100, 100, 1000)$ within the range of soft constraints and by $Q_s = \text{diag}(10^4, 10^4, 10^4)$ during their violation. Inputs are penalized by matrix $Q_u = \text{diag}(25, 100)$. The prediction horizon has been set to $N = 20$. The soft constraints for system states in deviation form are given as $[-15, -15, -15]^T \leq x \leq [15, 15, 15]^T$ and hard constraints for the control variables as $[-50, -40]^T \leq u \leq [50, 60]^T$.

3.4 Neural Network Approximation of Model Predictive Control

This paper's selection of Neural Network (NN) structure and activation functions is based on observations from our previous work (Kalúz et al., 2023). To approximate the behavior of the designed MPC, we have chosen MLP NN with two fully connected layers with 50 and 30 neurons containing activation functions in the form of polynomial approximations of hyperbolic tangent, and a single linear output layer (Fig. 3). In our case, the number of NN layers is directly limited by a maximum number of consecutive multiplications that a still practical CKKS setup can handle. The number of neurons in layers was selected based on empirical observations from numerous training and validation sessions.

To gather the training data for the NN, we generated a set of state combinations as follows. A state space for the MPC in deviation form was quantized to 50 uniformly spaced values between -25°C and 25°C (resolution of 1°C). This range accommodates both the state constraints ($-15^\circ\text{C} \leq x \leq 15^\circ\text{C}$) as well as space for their additional violation ($\pm 10^\circ\text{C}$) to activate the soft constraint

Fig. 3. Structure of implemented neural network for MPC approximation

penalization. In total, 125000 combinations of three quantized states were generated, and by applying them to MPC, we obtained corresponding control actions. MPC was implemented in MATLAB, using Multi-Parametric Toolbox 3.0 (Herceg et al., 2013), YALMIP (Löfberg, 2004), and LCP as a QP solver. Before the NN training, the state variables and control inputs were normalized between -1 and 1 . The 80% of randomly shuffled samples was used for training, and the remainder was equally split into two groups, one for validation and one for testing. The polynomial approximation of hyperbolic tangent in form $f(x) = 0.0009x^5 - 0.0392x^3 + 0.6414x$ was used as an activation function during the training. Using an Adam Optimizer, the NN was trained in Python using the Keras deep learning API. The training was done through 500 epochs with a batch size of 300 and a learning rate of 0.001. A mean square error has been chosen as a loss function. The whole training process was done on unencrypted data.

Fig. 4. Comparison between the original MPC and the MPC-mimicking neural network. The top figure shows the evolution of the system's states (temperatures), and the bottom figure shows the corresponding control actions (pump commands).

To evaluate the performance of MPC-mimicking NN compared to original MPC, we set up a closed-loop simulation to control the states of the model (1) to the origin represented by a steady state $x^s = [T_1^s, T_2^s, T_3^s]^T = [62.0^\circ\text{C}, 70.1^\circ\text{C}, 62.3^\circ\text{C}]^T$, and corresponding input $u^s =$

$[P_H^s, P_F^s] = [50\%, 40\%]$. To demonstrate the control to the origin, we set up the initial conditions to be $x_0 = [-10, 10, -20]^T + x^s$. We performed two additional input overrides at times 1000s and 2000s to showcase the disturbance rejection capabilities. The first disturbance set both control pumps to 0% and lasted for 25 seconds (5 samples). The second disturbance set both pumps to 100% and lasted 100 seconds to invoke a soft constraint state violation. The control trends are shown in Fig. 4. The trends show that trained NN approximates the original MPC well, especially during the standard operation, where the state and control trajectories are nearly identical. After the 2000 seconds of operation, a minor deviation can be observed. The root mean square errors between MPC and NN are $x_{\text{RMSE}} = [0.136^\circ\text{C}, 0.491^\circ\text{C}, 0.146^\circ\text{C}]$ for the state variables and $u_{\text{RMSE}} = [0.917\%, 0.347\%]$ for control variables. The mean absolute errors are $x_{\text{MAE}} = [0.659^\circ\text{C}, 1.038^\circ\text{C}, 0.805^\circ\text{C}]$ and $u_{\text{MAE}} = [4.698\%, 1.808\%]$ respectively.

4. SETUP FOR ENCRYPTED CONTROL

To perform NN-based approximated optimal control of the pasteurization unit over the encrypted data, we set up the CKKS cryptosystem parameters as follows. We selected the scaling factor Δ to be 37 bits long, and individual bit sizes of coefficient modulus $\mathcal{Q} = \mathcal{Q}_{S1} \times \mathcal{Q}_{\Delta1} \times \dots \times \mathcal{Q}_{\Delta M} \times \mathcal{Q}_{S2}$ to be $[45, 37, 37, 37, 37, 37, 37, 37, 37, 37, 45]$. The number of inner primes is 9, which defines the maximum allowed multiplicative depth. The sizes of outer primes in \mathcal{Q} were selected to be 45 bits long. According to configuration guideline (Furka et al., 2023) and Homomorphic Encryption Standard (Albrecht et al., 2018), the selected setup provides numerical precision of approximately 29 bits after the decimal point and 8 bits precision of integer part of numbers. The smaller integer part precision was selected on purpose since all the encrypted numbers propagated through NN are normalized to $\langle -1, 1 \rangle$. The smallest usable polynomial modulus degree that provides at least 128 bits security level is $N = 16384$.

The general arrangement of the control scenario implemented in this paper is shown in Fig. 5. We control the laboratory pasteurization unit by an MPC control law approximated by the NN, trained and tested in Sec. 3.4. The controlled process resides in a private (trusted) environment, and we programmatically simulate the scenario where the controller is outsourced to the other party (e.g. cloud computer) for the evaluation. In the implemented setup, we simulate this arrangement by running two separate environments on a single computer, one that interfaces with the process using MATLAB/Simulink and Python, and the second that evaluates the control law, implemented in Python and TenSEAL crypto library (Benaissa et al., 2021).

During control, the state variables (temperatures) are measured at every sampling instance and normalized to $\langle -1, 1 \rangle$. The states are then encrypted into ciphertext using the private key and sent to an outsourced NN controller for homomorphic evaluation. The process of NN inference requires a set of keys provided to the other party in advance. The inference of NN outputs a ciphertext with encrypted control action that is then sent to the process

side to be decrypted, rescaled, and applied to the process. It is important to note that the parameters of trained NNs are kept in plaintext, and only the process states and control actions are encrypted.

Fig. 5. Diagram of scenario for control evaluation over encrypted data

The control evaluation was done on a computer with AMD Ryzen 9 3950X CPU and 128GB of RAM. All the computations were run on a CPU in a single-threaded execution with an average clock speed of approximately 4.2GHz. The encrypted control setup was tested for both evaluation time and memory footprint. On average, the cumulative time for encoding and encryption of states took 20.8ms, while decryption and decoding of control actions took 1.4ms. The evaluation time of NN took, on average, 690.5ms, which is well within the sampling time of 5 seconds. The public and secret key sizes were 2.02MB and 1.01MB, respectively, while rotational and re-linearization keys occupied 525.9MB and 20.23MB. The average size of a ciphertext was 1.81MB.

5. CONTROL OF PASTEURIZATION UNIT OVER ENCRYPTED DATA

For the experiment on the laboratory pasteurization unit we have performed three consecutive scenarios to control the process to selected steady state, represented by temperatures $x^s = [55^\circ\text{C}, 66^\circ\text{C}, 55.5^\circ\text{C}]^T$ that correspond to input setup $u^s = [50\%, 40\%]^T$. Firstly, we controlled the process by the original MPC (3), then by an NN MPC over plain data, and lastly, by an NN MPC over encrypted data, using the setup in Sec. 4. We have tried replicating the same initial and operating conditions for all three experiments. However, some discrepancies in results will always be present due to the sensitivity of the process to external factors and disturbances and the overall nature of using a real process.

The process was controlled for a duration of 1400 seconds, with sampling time $T_s = 5\text{s}$. We have performed two simulated disturbances by stalling both control pumps, firstly by turning the pumps off at the time 250s for 50 seconds and then turning them fully on at 700s for 50 seconds.

The applied disturbances can be seen in Figure 6 with their corresponding effects on the temperatures in Figure 7. All

Fig. 6. Feed and heating pump command trajectories for MPC, NN-MPC and encrypted setup

Fig. 7. Temperature trajectories within pasteurization unit during the control by an MPC, NN-MPC, and encrypted setup

three control implementations provide satisfactory performance in rejecting the disturbances and recovering the pasteurization temperature to close vicinity of the standard operating conditions. As previously shown in Fig. 4 (Sec. 3.4), the performance of the trained NN is expected to be very close to the original MPC. Similar behavior can

be observed in the results acquired from the real process. The performance comparison of pasteurization control (both real process and simulation) is numerically presented in Table 1 using two integral criteria: the Integral Square Error (ISE) and Integral Absolute Error (IAE).

Table 1. Performance Comparison Between MPC, NN-MPC, and NN-MPC over Encrypted Data

	ISE (T_1, T_2, T_3) [$^{\circ}\text{C}$]	IAE (T_1, T_2, T_3) [$^{\circ}\text{C}$]
Integral criteria rel. to orig. T_1^s, T_2^s, T_3^s (real process)		
MPC	$[1.26, 0.469, 1.38] \times 10^4$	$[1.81, 1.03, 1.89] \times 10^3$
NN	$[1.33, 0.582, 1.44] \times 10^4$	$[1.85, 1.16, 1.93] \times 10^3$
NN (E)	$[1.23, 0.347, 1.34] \times 10^4$	$[1.78, 0.862, 1.86] \times 10^3$
Integral criteria rel. to orig. T_1^s, T_2^s, T_3^s (simulation)		
MPC	$[0.743, 2.73, 0.710] \times 10^4$	$[1.33, 3.68, 1.27] \times 10^3$
NN	$[0.767, 2.82, 0.732] \times 10^4$	$[1.32, 3.87, 1.27] \times 10^3$
NN (E)	$[0.705, 2.27, 0.683] \times 10^4$	$[1.21, 3.45, 1.23] \times 10^3$
Integral criteria rel. to MPC performance (simulation)		
NN	$[0.018, 0.241, 3.44] \times 10^3$	$[0.085, 0.403, 0.856] \times 10^3$
NN (E)	$[0.049, 0.111, 3.37] \times 10^3$	$[0.190, 0.971, 0.908] \times 10^3$

6. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, we have shown that homomorphically evaluated optimal control, which closely appropriates the original behavior, can be implemented in real processes for the cost of some compromises. The first is the approximation itself, which does not provide strict guarantees for the optimal solution, stability, and constraint satisfaction. Another compromise comes in the form of significant computational and memory overhead. The main benefit of the presented setup is the ability to preserve data privacy in network control systems to protect the process operation against industrial espionage.

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